

A Case Using Wire Fixation for Mandible Fractures: A Simple and Cost-Effective Technique

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ABSTRACT

Background: Mandibular fractures are among the most common facial injuries, often caused by traffic accidents, or sports-related trauma. These fractures frequently involve the symphysis and condylar process of the mandible, structures essential for masticatory function and jaw articulation.

Case: A 43 years female presented to emergency department following a traffic accident with complaints of severe jaw pain, particularly when moving or opening the mouth. CT scan confirmed a mandibular symphysis fracture and bilateral dislocated mandibular condylar process fractures.

Intervention and Management: Intervention included wire fixation of the mandibular symphysis, arch bar placement on both the maxilla and mandible, And rubber arch bar for additional stabilization.

Discussion: This Intervention and management have demonstrated efficacy in ensuring jaw stability. Wire fixation is often chosen as a simple and cost-effective alternative. However, complications such as infection, TMJ dysfunction, and malocclusion may arise if postoperative recovery is suboptimal.

Conclusion: Wire fixation remains a viable treatment modality for mandibular fractures, particularly in settings with technological or financial constraints. Appropriate technique selection and postoperative care are critical to achieving optimal functional outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Mandibular fracture, TMJ dislocation, Wire fixation

INTRODUCTION

Mandibular fractures are a common facial injury, mainly resulting from physical trauma such as traffic accidents, physical violence, or sports accidents. Various methods of treating mandibular fractures have evolved over time, from conservative treatment to more advanced surgical techniques such as open reduction and internal fixation. However, one technique that remains relevant, especially in situations where both cost and technology are limited, is the use of wire fixation. Wire fixation offers a simple, effective and cost-effective approach to managing mandibular fractures, especially in less complex fracture cases.³ Although more modern methods exist, wire fixation remains the first choice in many cases, especially in resource-constrained settings.⁴ Given its advantages in terms of cost and simplicity, this technique is widely used in patients with mandibular fractures that not require complex surgical management.

ARTICLE DETAILS

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CASE ILLUSTRATION

A 43-year-old female presented to the emergency room with jaw pain, especially when opening or moving her jaw, following a motorcycle accident. She reported pain in both cheeks and the chin, without limb weakness, fainting, nausea, or vomiting. Edema, deformity, and tenderness were observed on both cheeks, with excoriation and hematoma on the chin. CT scan revealed a minimally displaced mandibular symphysis fracture and displaced bilateral mandibular condylar process fractures (Figure 1).

Figure 1. CT scan of Head (a) mandibular symphysis fracture, minimally displaced (b,c) right and left mandibular condylar process fractures displace.

INTERVENTION AND MANAGEMENT

The patient was admitted and diagnosed with bilateral mandibular condylus fracture+ mandibular symphysis fracture + bilateral TMJ dislocation. The patient underwent ORIF Wire + Maxillomandibular Fixation Arch Bar + TMJ Repositioning.

Bilateral TMJ repositioning was performed (Figure 2). A mandibular symphysis fracture was found, then inserted with wire (2 pieces) on the mandibular symphysis (Figure 3). After that, arch bars were placed on the maxilla and mandible (Figure 4). The mandibular vestibular section was sutured layer by layer with 3-0 water tight vicryl. After that, rubber was attached to the maxilla and mandible arch bar.

Figure 2. Temporomandibular joint repositioning

Figure 3. (a) Mandibular symphysis fracture (b) wire insertion.

Figure 4. Arch bar placement on the maxilla and mandible.

DISCUSSION

In this case, the patient had bilateral mandibular symphysis and mandibular condyle process fractures with bilateral temporomandibular joint (TMJ) dislocations, caused by a traffic accident.

Mandibular fractures, involving the symphysis and condyle process, require a careful approach as they involve important functions such as bite and jaw articulation. The decision to perform ORIF with maxillomandibular fixation (MMF) was appropriate given the dislocation of the condyle and symphysis fractures.

Bilateral TMJ repositioning is performed first to reposition the affected temporomandibular joint. In mandibular symphysis fractures and arch bar placement on the maxilla and mandible is an effective treatment option in these cases. The placement of wires helps in stabilization of the separated bone fragments, while the use of MMF reduces jaw movements that may aggravate the dislocation or cause dental misalignment after healing.

In general, treatment for mandibular fractures can be divided into three main categories: expectant management, closed treatment (MMF), and open surgical treatment such as ORIF. ⁶ In situations of limited resources, wire fixation is often chosen as a simple and cost-effective alternative, although this technique is not always chosen for more complex fracture cases. The use of wire fixation in mandibular fractures is particularly effective in fractures of the symphysis or other parts that do not heavily involve dental structures or the TMJ. ^{7,8}

The disadvantages of wire fixation is such as infection, impaired TMJ function, or malocclusion. These complications are more common in patients with fractures involving more complex body parts or when wire fixation is not performed carefully. Therefore, although wire fixation remains a widely used technique, proper patient selection and adequate surgical skills are essential to minimize the risk of long-term complications.

After wire fixation, patient recovery requires careful nursing care and regular monitoring to identify complications such as infection or dental misalignment (malocclusion). Physical therapy and follow-up examinations to check TMJ joint function and jaw stability are essential to ensure optimal recovery. Even if repositioning is performed, bilateral TMJ dislocation can cause impaired masticatory function and even long-term pain in patients. Failure to ensure proper restoration of tooth and jaw position can lead to malocclusion, which can affect the patient's masticatory function and facial aesthetics. Considering the aspects of effectiveness, cost-efficiency, as well as ease of application, the use of wire fixation for mandibular fractures remains a viable option for treating these injuries, especially in resource-constrained situations or in areas with limited access to advanced medical technology. ⁷

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The prognosis for these patients is generally good. Patients are expected to return to normal function after a few weeks of treatment and recovery, with regular checks to ensure no complications arise. During the recovery period, monitoring for malocclusion and TMJ function is essential to ensure optimal recovery.

CONCLUSION

Wire fixation is a simple and cost-effective technique for treating mandibular fractures, particularly in resource-limited environments. While newer fixation methods are available, wire fixation remains a practical and widely used approach. Careful patient selection, proper surgical technique, and diligent postoperative management are essential to achieving optimal treatment outcomes.

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